

Polarographic and Cyclic Voltammetric Reduction of *o*-Hydroxybenzaldehyde Isonicotinoylhydrazone

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o-Hydroxybenzaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone (*o*-OH-BAINH) exhibits two waves in solutions of pH 2-8 while one wave has made its appearance in solution of pH 9. However, the cyclic voltammogram of the compound exhibits three cathodic peaks in acid solutions and two cathodic peaks in alkaline solutions. The electrode reactions are attributed to the reductive cleavage of =N-N- linkage and the reduction of the amide formed in the cleavage.

ISONICOTINOYLHYDRAZIDE derivatives of carbonyl compounds are used extensively as therapeutic agents¹⁻⁴. *o*-Hydroxybenzaldehyde isonicotinoylhydrazone (*o*-OH-BAINH) with the structure $o\text{-HO}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$, is one of such compounds. This compound offers interesting features for electrochemical reduction studies, since it possesses more than one reducible sites in its molecule. The authors have therefore undertaken polarographic and cyclic voltammetric studies in solutions of pH 2 to 9.

Experimental

o-OH-BAINH was prepared by refluxing a mixture (1 : 1) of *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and isonicotinoylhydrazone for 2 h. The product was purified by repeated recrystallisation from hot aqueous alcohol. The compound was characterised by infrared spectral data, elemental analysis and melting point (252°, lit. 252-53°). All the chemicals used in the investigations were of AnalaR grade.

Current-voltage curves were recorded in Britton-Robinson buffers (pH 2-9) with a Elico CL 25 DC pen recording polarograph. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics: $t=3.0$ s, $m=1.93$ mg s⁻¹ at a height of 85 cm of mercury column in water under open-circuit conditions. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded with a model 174 A, Applied Research Company (U.S.A.) polarographic coupled with an X-Y recorder (model 0074) and Universal Programmer (Model 175), hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE, Metrohm 9323), platinum wire electrode and SCE were used as working electrode, counter electrode and reference electrode, respectively. The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

Electrochemical reduction in acid solutions: *o*-OH-BAINH exhibits two waves in acid solutions

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF *o*-OH-BAINH

pH	-E _{1/2} (V) vs SCE	
	First wave	Second wave
2.0	0.74	0.89
3.0	0.79	0.97
4.0	0.85	1.05
5.0	0.92	1.10
6.0	0.99	1.17
7.0	1.06	1.22
8.0	1.12	1.23
9.0	—	1.24

TABLE 2—PEAK POTENTIALS OF *o*-OH-BAINH

Sweep rate Vs ⁻¹	-E _{pcI/IV} , -E _{pcII/IV} , -E _{pcIII/IV}		
	pH 4.0		
0.050	0.86	1.02	1.20
0.100	0.87	1.04	1.21
	pH 8.0		
0.050	1.18	1.29	—
0.100	1.19	1.30	—

(pH 2-8). Typical polarograms are shown in Figs. 1a and 2a. Semilogarithmic analysis of the wave reveals that the wave is irreversible. The limiting current varied linearly with the concentration of the hydrazone and with the square root of the mercury column height. These facts indicate that the wave is diffusion-controlled. Half-wave potential shifts towards more negative values with increase in pH as per the equations,

$$\text{I-wave, } E_{1/2} = -0.60 - 0.067 \times \text{pH}$$

$$\text{II-wave, } E_{1/2} = -0.78 - 0.067 \times \text{pH}$$

suggesting that protons are taking part in the reduction process.

Fig. 1. (a) Typical polarogram of *o*-OH-BAINH at pH 4.0 (initial voltage, -0.6 V), and (b) typical cyclic voltammogram of *o*-OH-BAINH at pH 4.0 (initial voltage, -0.7 V; sweep rate, 100 mV s^{-1}).

Fig. 2. (a) Typical polarogram of *o*-OH-BAINH at pH 8.0 (initial voltage, -0.9 V), and (b) typical cyclic voltammogram of *o*-OH-BAINH at pH 8.0 (initial voltage, -1.0 V; sweep rate, 100 mV s^{-1}).

The cyclic voltammogram of the hydrazone showed three cathodic peaks in acid solutions in the forward scan. Typical voltammogram is shown in Fig. 1b. In reverse scan, no peak is observed. This suggests the irreversible nature of the electrode process. This is also confirmed by the negative shift in the peak potentials with increasing sweep rates.

The total number of electrons involved in the polarographic reduction process are established as two and four respectively for the first and second waves. The first wave is ascribed to the reductive cleavage of =N-N-linkage involving two electrons. The second wave is attributed to the reduction of the amide to alcohol on the basis of the

position of the wave on the potential axis and on the basis of the product analysis.

In cyclic voltammetry three cathodic peaks are noticed in acid solutions. From the position of the peaks on the potential axis, the first peak is attributed to the two-electron reductive cleavage of =N-N- bond. The second peak is ascribed to the intermediate and the third peak to the reduction of the intermediate to alcohol. However, in the polarographic studies, a single wave is obtained in place of the second and third peaks in view of the slow scan rate of the potential in polarography.

Electrochemical reduction in alkaline solutions: *o*-OH-BAINH exhibits two polarographic waves in alkaline solutions. The effect of mercury column height and concentration on the wave height suggests that the waves are diffusion-controlled. The wave is found irreversible by the semilogarithmic analysis.

The cyclic voltammogram of the compound exhibits two cathodic peaks in the forward scan. Typical voltammogram is shown in Fig. 2b. In the reverse scan, no peak is observed. This fact

indicates the irreversible nature of the electrode process. This is also confirmed by the negative shift in the peak potentials with increasing sweep rates. The first wave is ascribed to the reductive cleavage of =N-N- linkage in the compound. Similar wave was reported in isonicotinoylhydrazide⁵. The second wave is due to the reduction of the amide to alcohol. It was reported in literature that amides undergo reduction to the corresponding alcohols⁶.

The observations made in polarographic studies are in agreement with those made in cyclic voltammetric studies, and the half-wave potentials agree well with the peak potentials. A single peak in the medium shows that both the steps (corresponding to peak-II and peak-III in acid medium) takes place at the same potential in the medium.

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